

Primary Dentition Canal Sealing Techniques: An Update

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Abstract: Pulpectomy is an essential procedure in pediatric dentistry aimed at preserving primary teeth affected by irreversible pulpitis or pulpal necrosis until their natural exfoliation. The success of pulpectomy largely depends on adequate cleaning, shaping and obturation of the root canal system. Obturation in primary teeth is challenging due to anatomical variations such as accessory canals, physiologic root resorption and curved root canals. Various obturation techniques have been introduced to achieve optimal canal filling while minimizing voids and overfilling. These techniques are broadly classified into syringe-based and non-syringe techniques. Commonly used methods include lentulospiral, incremental filling technique, bidirectional spiral, Pastinject, pressure syringe, disposable syringe, capillary tips, and NaviTip systems. Several studies have evaluated these techniques based on parameters such as length of obturation, presence of voids, apical seal, and clinical success. Although no single technique has been proven superior in all situations, lentulospiral and NaviTip techniques have demonstrated promising results in achieving optimal canal filling. This review aims to discuss various obturating techniques used in primary teeth along with their advantages, limitations, and evidence from previous studies.

Keywords: Primary teeth, Pulpectomy, Obturation, Lentulospiral, NaviTip, Pediatric endodontics

Introduction

In the early stages, extraction was the primary method of treating pulpally affected primary teeth in order to reduce pain and infection. However, conservative treatment methods like pulpotomy and pulpectomy have gained popularity due to developments in paediatric dentistry and endodontic therapy. ^[1] In pulpectomy, necrotic or infected pulp tissue is removed, and the root canal system is then cleaned, shaped and obturated using a resorbable substance. The goal of pulp therapy for primary teeth is to keep the tooth functioning until it naturally exfoliates while preventing infection and harm to the permanent replacement. ^[2] A good root canal seal guarantees periapical tissue repair and inhibits microbiological reinfection. ^[3,4] However, because of their intricate canal shape, physiological root resorption, and close proximity to growing permanent tooth buds, obturation in primary teeth is difficult. ^[5,6] A number of methods, such as progressive filling, lentulospiral technique, syringe techniques, and pressure delivery systems, have been developed for obturation in primary teeth. Radiography, digital imaging, dye penetration investigations, and CBCT analysis have all been used to assess these methods. ^[7,8]

Obturation History in Primary Teeth

As early as 1932, root canal therapy was promoted as a way to save main teeth that would otherwise need to be extracted because of pulpal infection. ^[9] As other materials and delivery methods were developed, the idea of obturation changed. After being discovered by Bonastre in 1837 and brought to dentistry by Chisholm in 1876, zinc oxide eugenol went on to become a widely utilized obturating material. Sweet (1930) suggested zinc oxide eugenol is easy to work with and has antibacterial qualities. In order to cure pulp necrosis, Buckley (1904) developed a formaldehyde–glycerin mixture. This led to the creation of pulpectomy techniques, which involve removing infected pulp tissue and filling it with resorbable materials. ^[10,11] According to O'Riordan and Coll, early obturation techniques depend on the hand positioning of materials using pluggers or reamers. Kopel then suggested using hand-held lentulospirals, which enhanced the root canal system's filling material dispersion. The mechanical syringe technique was later developed by Greenberg (1971), which made it possible to transfer obturating material into canals under regulated conditions. The jiffy tube technique, capillary tip systems, and endodontic pressure syringes were further developments aimed at minimizing void formation and improving obturation quality. ^[9] Clinicians now have more options for obtaining the best obturation in primary teeth because to these advancements.

Obturing Techniques Used in Primary Dentition

Classification of root canal obturation techniques for primary teeth:

Syringe Techniques	Non-Syringe Techniques
Disposable Needle	Lentulospiral
Insulin Syringe	Bi-Directional Spiral
Tuberculin Syringe	Incremental Technique (Endodontic Pluggers)
NaviTip	Past Inject
Pressure syringe	
Capillary Tips	
Jiffy Tube	

Incremental Filling Techniques

Gould developed the incremental filling procedure in 1972. It entails employing an endodontic plugger with a rubber stopper to insert thick zinc oxide eugenol paste into the canal. The obturating material is injected in sequential increments of about 2 mm until the canal is fully filled, while the plugger length is kept about 2 mm short of the working length.^[12] This technique enables precise material placement, which aids in controlling the quantity of obturating material into the canal. However, pluggers are less effective in narrow and curved canals, which are frequently present in primary teeth, due to their limited flexibility. Furthermore, the likelihood of void formation may be increased by repeatedly moving the plugger while applying the paste.^[13]

Lentulospiral Technique

One of the most popular techniques for obturating primary teeth is the lentulospiral technique, which was created by Kopel. This method involves coating a lentulospiral which is attached to a slow-speed handpiece into the obturating paste and inserting it into the canal to the desired working length. To equally distribute the paste along the canal sides, the device is rotated. Kahn et al. (1997) found that lentulospirals revolving at 5,000 rpm are more suited for the cervical and middle thirds of the canal, those rotating at 15,000 rpm are more effective in filling the apical third. The flexibility and straightforward design enables even paste distribution in curved channels, make the method popular. However, disadvantages include the possibility of material extrusion beyond the apex, the difficulty of setting the rubber stop, and the risk of instrument breakage.^[14]

Bi-Directional Spiral Technique

Barry Musikant created the bi-directional spiral technique in 1988. It makes use of a specially made file with two opposing spirals meeting at the centre. The obturating material is directed coronally by the apical spiral and apically by the coronal spiral. The material spreads laterally along the canal walls at the intersection of the spirals. Reduced apical extrusion, limited vacuum formation and controlled material flow are all made possible by this design. A slow-speed handpiece is used to mount the instrument, which is then progressively removed while rotating until the canal seems to be fully filled. ^[11]

Past-Inject Technique

Similar to a lentulospiral, Past-Inject (Micromega) is an engine-driven device with a flattened blade design that enhances obturating material delivery. Its helical shape creates a translational movement that enables even paste distribution along the canal walls, and its great flexibility enables it to follow the root canal's natural curve. Excellent flexibility, accurate material placement, and better obturation quality with less canal transportation are some of this technique's benefits. ^[11]

A. (Endodontic Pluggers)

B. (Bi-Directional Spiral)

C. (Past-Inject)

D (Lentulospiral)

Syringe Techniques

Endodontic Pressure Syringe

A syringe barrel, threaded plugger, wrench, and threaded needle make up the endodontic pressure syringe, which was created by Greenberg and detailed by Krakow and Berk in 1965. Controlled pressure is used to introduce a standardised mixture of obturating material into the canal. The screw mechanism progressively pushes the material into the canal while the needle is removed at 3-mm intervals. The needle is placed into the canal until resistance is felt. The pressure-generating screw mechanism, which enables deeper material penetration into the canal and produces ideal filling, is the technique's primary benefit. However, because of physiological root resorption, overfilling is frequently seen in primary teeth. ^[9]

Mechanical Syringe Technique

Greenberg introduced the mechanical syringe technique in 1971 as an easy and affordable way to obturate primary teeth. Obturating paste is injected into the canal using a 2-ml or 5-ml disposable syringe and a 24-gauge needle. The material is injected gradually while the needle is removed from the canal after it has been inserted to the predefined length. ^[15] The disposable syringe lowers the risk of cross-infection, and this method is simple to use, affordable, and suitable with a variety of obturating agents.

Tuberculin and Insulin Syringe Techniques

Using a 26-gauge needle and light finger pressure, obturating paste is administered using the tuberculin syringe technique. Studies have shown that, in comparison to other methods, this approach has a longer obturation and more void formation, despite its simplicity and affordability. ^[13] The similar idea underlies the insulin syringe approach as well. The obturating material is administered while the needle is gradually removed from the canal using a syringe that comprises of a needle, barrel, and plunger. But according to Hiremath et al. (2016), insulin syringes might yield worse outcomes than pressure syringes, especially when it comes to apical extrusion and void formation. ^[16,17]

NaviTip System

A thin, flexible metal cannula that comes in a variety of gauges and lengths makes up the NaviTip delivery system. Its flexible tip makes it simple to navigate into curved canals and for precise insertion of obturating material close to the apex. NaviTip successfully stopped material from extruding past the apex, according to Memarpour et al. (2013), however incomplete obturation was occasionally seen. Similarly, although lentulospiral showed a higher incidence of voids, Khubchandani et al. (2018) reported no significant difference in apical sealing ability between lentulospiral and NaviTip methods. ^[18]

H (NaviTip System)

Discussion

Dental caries is the most common oral health condition in the world, despite significant advancements in preventive dentistry in recent decades. ^[19] In addition to prevent harmful oral habits and maintaining arch length as a natural space maintainer, the preservation of pulpally involved primary teeth is crucial for sustaining mastication, aesthetics, phonetics, and appropriate occlusal development. In order to preserve the tooth in a functioning state until its natural exfoliation, pulpectomy is still a frequently used therapeutic option for primary teeth with permanently inflamed or necrotic pulp. ^[20]

Achieving a three-dimensional fluid-tight seal throughout the root canal system is crucial to the effectiveness of endodontic therapy. However, achieving the best obturation is extremely difficult due to the structural complexity of primary teeth, which includes auxiliary canals, secondary dentin deposition, complex canals, and continuous physiological root resorption. ^[21] Camp highlighted that an in-depth knowledge of primary pulp morphology, root formation, and resorption patterns—all of which are very different from those of permanent dentition is necessary for effective endodontic therapy in primary teeth. ^[22]

Many obturation methods have been developed and tested in both in vitro and in vivo investigations to solve these issues. These methods can be broadly divided into two categories: non-syringe methods (such as lentulospiral, incremental filling, endodontic plugger, bi-directional spiral, and Past-Inject) and syringe methods (like disposable syringes, pressure syringes, capillary tips, and NaviTip systems). While NaviTip and disposable syringe techniques are commonly employed among syringe-based procedures because of their convenience of material administration and shorter obturation time, lentulospiral has long been considered as the gold standard among non-syringe methods. ^[22,23]

However, the use of needles in syringe techniques may induce anxiety in young patients, which can impair compliance and ultimately impact the quality of obturation. ^[13] When compared to alternative methods, Rajasekhar et al. showed that syringe-based procedures considerably shortened obturation time. ^[24] Using criteria developed by Coll and Sadrian and other researchers, the majority of studies assessing obturation quality have concentrated on radiographic indicators such as apical seal, void development, and amount of obturation. ^[10,11,12] Although pressure syringes may raise the risk of overfilling, NaviTip systems have demonstrated promising results among syringe techniques, whereas lentulospiral frequently exhibits excellent obturation among non-syringe approaches. ^[13] Regardless of approach, void formation is somehow frequently observed and may potentially compromise treatment outcomes by allowing microleakage and microbial survival. ^[24] The delivery method, operator skill, experience, consistency and viscosity of the obturating material are the factors that affect the creation of voids. ^[25,26] Furthermore, regular clinical and radiographical follow-up is crucial because radiographic examination by itself cannot establish long-term success. After a six-month follow-up, Bawazir et al. found that rotary lentulospiral had greater clinical and radiographic success rates than the hand-held method. ^[26]

Conclusion

Obturation in primary dentition is a crucial step in endodontic treatment, requiring careful consideration of various techniques and materials. This review highlights the diversity of obturation methods, including syringe and non-syringe techniques, each with its advantages and limitations. Syringe techniques, such as NaviTip and disposable syringes, offer ease of use and control, while non-syringe techniques, like Lentulospiral and Past Inject, provide unique benefits in specific situations. In pediatric dentistry, where patient cooperation and anxiety play a significant role, selecting an appropriate obturation technique is vital. Clinicians must weigh the benefits and drawbacks of each method, considering factors like ease of use, material properties, and patient comfort. Ultimately, achieving optimal obturation in primary teeth requires a comprehensive understanding of the techniques, materials, and unique challenges involved. By staying updated on the latest research and advancements, clinicians can provide high-quality care, ensuring the best possible outcomes for their young patients.

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